

NDAC/LO/071

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, II.

by S. Söderhjelm

1. Introduction

In the previous papers NDAC/LO/066 ("I") and NDAC/LO/067 ("Ib") a simulation/solution program was described and used for wide ($\text{sep} > 1''$) binaries. It was implicitly assumed that a priori data were available in order to start the LS-fitting close to the real element set. In the present paper, the required accuracy of this a priori knowledge is investigated, and a "double iteration" scheme is proposed to find previously unknown systems with separations less than some 1.2 arcsec.

2. Convergence of the LS-fitting

In Paper I, "a few tenths of an arcsec" was given as the required accuracy in the start elements for correct convergence. Normally, the parallax and proper motions may be put initially to zero, what matters is the four position offsets (two coordinates for each component). The position variables are the primary x_2, x_3 and the relative x_8, x_9 (cf. Paper I). The start values of x_2, x_3 were now taken at ϵ_1 arcsec from the true position, and those for x_8, x_9 at ϵ_2 arcsec from the true separation (in random position angles). The dependence on the individual ϵ_i is rather similar, and the relevant parameter seems to be $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1^2 + \epsilon_2^2)^{1/2}$. A large number of tests has been made for the standard Ser. C with two equal 8^m.5-stars. Usually, the data for a single binary was analyzed with several different starting errors in the solution-program, and the convergence or non-convergence noted. This part of the work was done while hunting down some disturbing program bugs, thus no planned survey was made. When data from the various runs is put together (Table 1), a rather definite pattern emerges, however.

Table 1. Percentage of non-converged solutions as function of the binary separation and the overall start error ϵ . All data are for Ser C-binaries, and the figures in parentheses give the total number of attempted solutions.

Sep\ ϵ	<.2	.2-.3	.3-.4	.4-.5	>.5
<1"	4 (46)	12 (58)	21 (101)	60 (43)	100 (3)
1"-2"	0 (28)	0 (62)	6 (123)	42 (65)	78 (9)
>2"		0 (8)	2 (90)	24 (86)	41 (17)

As expected, the rate of unsuccessful solutions increases with ϵ , but there is also a definite dependence on the separation. For the wide binaries treated in Paper I, there are no problems for $\epsilon < 0''.3-0''.4$. For the closer systems, there are difficulties even for $\epsilon < 0''.2$. Much fewer runs were made for unequal binaries, but the results in Table 1 seem fairly general. The main conclusion from this is that most known binaries will have ϵ small enough to assure convergent LS-fits to the data at hand. The interesting point is the unknown binaries.

3. Double iteration for unknown binaries

In practice, a lot of stars will be flagged in the preprocessing stage as difficult to fit by a single star model. The next simplest assumption is then a physical binary (equal parallax for the two components) but possibly unequal (linear) proper motion components. Nothing is known a priori about the intensity ratio or the separation between the components (other than that it is very probably less than 1-2 arcsec).

We try now to use systematically a series of different starting parameters in order to find the "best" possible solution. At the binary fitting stage of the reductions, the main solution will allow the photocentre of the suspected star to be almost perfectly located. The main uncertainty lies in the position and intensity of an eventual secondary component. The intensity ratio acts linearly in the observation equations, and an a priori assumption that $\Delta m = 1$ magnitude is sufficient to assure convergence in this respect. The observation equations diverge for zero separation, thus we have to assume a separation and a position angle. From some mathematical considerations (about covering the largest possible circle with a number of smaller circles), a 12-point search-grid pattern is defined by the following separations and position angles:

igrd = 1-4 : Sep = s ; PA = 45,135,225,315⁰
 igrd = 5-12 : Sep = (1+√2) s ; PA = 0,45,90, ...,315⁰

The "grid-size" s has to be optimized in order to catch all systems with small separations and still reach to as large separations as possible. From a large number of (mostly) Ser C runs, the value s=0".35 has been adopted, but 0".40 may be equally good. (At s=0".50 more than a third of the solutions for close systems do not converge). With s= 0".35, the upper limit for the binary separations is about 1".2, in good agreement with the results given in Section 1.

In practice then, the LS-solution is started with a secondary component ($\Delta m=1$) at grid point #1 for a first series of iterations. If the solution does not converge, the secondary is put at grid point #2 instead, and so on for at most 12 trials. An important parameter is then mxit, the maximum number of iterations to allow before proceeding to the next grid point. A large mxit may give convergence at "earlier" grid-points, but when convergence does not occur until "late" in the search, a large number of iterations are wasted. A small mxit may speed the search up, but at risk of never finding a converging solution. The present results show that the total number of iterations is rather insensitive to mxit, and a value mxit=12 has been provisionally adopted.

It is of course necessary to specify what is meant by a converged LS-solution. The main criterium is the (maximum) ratio of parameter corrections to mean errors at each iteration. This is typically about 100 in the first iterations, and a value below 0.1 is a first necessary indication of convergence. Secondly, the fit to the "observations" (Fourier coefficients) is tested by the standard χ^2 measure

$$S = \sum_{\text{obs}} \left(\frac{o-c}{\sigma} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

which should be close to nobs=4*nframes. At present, I allow a liberal 10-sigma deviation, rejecting only solutions with $S > \text{nobs} + (200*\text{nobs})^{1/2}$. I also count the number of observations deviating by more than 3 sigma. For a gaussian distribution, this should be some 0.003*nobs, and a rejection limit 0.015*nobs is formally applied. An LS-solution passing these three criteria is accepted by the program, but there may still be problems. (A solution may be rejected earlier if it behaves badly. At each iteration, the actual parameter values are checked, and e.g a clearly

unreasonable magnitude may indicate runaway. It has also been found convenient to constrain the magnitude difference to the interval $0 < \Delta m < 5$ mag.)

4. Convergence results

Because the above scheme for double-star handling is rather time-consuming, the statistics reported are for tens or hundreds of runs instead of (the ideal) thousands. All computations are for the "standard" position on the sky ($\alpha = 0$, $\delta = 35^{\circ}26'$) used in Paper I, and the magnitudes and colours of the stars are for Series A, B and C only. The IFOV pointing is described by $\sigma_F = 2''.5$, $\sigma_S = 0''.2$, and the observation time is always 4 slots (out of 20) per frame.

The programs have evolved continually, and there are too few uniform surveys, especially with regard to the speed of convergence. (As an example, for some time I tried to actually reject all discordant observations, using a rejection-limit shrinking towards 3 sigma as the number of iterations increased. This procedure appreciably slowed the speed of convergence by introducing "oscillations" when some observations were alternately rejected and re-introduced in successive iterations). Table 2 summarizes the convergence data obtained with later versions of the program. The number of failures (ndiv) is according to the criteria given in Section 3, but at large Δm there are also "false" solutions (nf) with the secondary misplaced by one or two slitwidths. (See further Section 5).

Table 2. Mean number of LS-iterations until convergence (nit), for different separation-intervals and for each of the three series A-C. Also given are the number of successful solutions (N), the number of non-converged solutions (ndiv), and the number of "false" solutions (nf).

Sep(")	C				B				A			
	nit	N	ndiv	nf	nit	N	ndiv	nf	nit	N	ndiv	nf
0.1-0.2	12	28	0	0	17	19	0	0	24	17	2	0
0.2-0.3	7	14	0	0	13	11	0	0	13	10	0	1
0.3-0.4	9	10	0	0	12	11	0	0	12	11	0	0
0.4-0.6	28	16	0	0	14	14	0	0	16	14	0	1
0.6-0.9	40	18	0	0	41	17	0	0	30	11	0	6
0.9-1.1	62	28	0	0	54	14	0	0	66	4	0	10
1.1-1.3	73	13	3	0	99	17	1	0	69	5	0	13

As seen from these numbers, the present method will generally find the correct solution for a binary with $\Delta m < 2$ and $0''.15 < \text{Sep} < 1''.1$. For separations about equal to the slit-width, the rate of non-converged solutions rises above 10%, and for Ser. A ($\Delta m = 3$), most of the solutions for $\text{Sep} > 1''$ has the secondary misplaced by one or two slit-widths.

5. The fit to the observations

As described in Section 3, the fit to the observations is given by the χ^2 -measure S and the number of large deviations nl . These are both close to their expected values, testifying that the weights are reasonably adjusted (cf. NDAC/LO/067). There is only a systematic trend with slightly smaller values for separations $0''.3 - 0''.9$ and larger ones at $0''.1 - 0''.3$ and $0''.9 - 1''.3$.

An interesting point concerns the limiting separation where a binary may be detected by large S and nl -values when a single-star solution is attempted. Table 3 gives mean S - and nl -values for single- and binary-solutions at several (small) values of the separation. It is apparent how the detection-limit rapidly gets larger with Δm . Note however, that if one for some other reason suspects duplicity, it is quite possible to find the correct binary solution even though a single-star solution fits the observations equally well.

Table 3. Mean S - and nl -values (with mean errors) for single- and binary-star solutions at different separations and magnitude-differences. (For a perfect gaussian fit, S should be $4 * \text{nobs} = 4704$, and $nl = 13$).

Sep(")	C($\Delta m = 0.$)				B($\Delta m = 1.5$)				A($\Delta m = 3.$)			
	S_s	S_b	nl_s	nl_b	S_s	S_b	nl_s	nl_b	S_s	S_b	nl_s	nl_b
0.10	5190	5040	26	22	4780	4790	14	16	4700	4720	14	14
	50	40	1	1	60	60	1	1	40	30	1	1
0.15	6680	5040	75	22	4990	4660	18	14	4660	4640	14	13
	150	60	5	2	60	20	1	1	40	50	1	1
0.25	16600	4880	570	19	6810	4680	67	14	4760	4600	14	12
	900	40	50	1	240	50	8	1	30	30	1	1
0.35					10400	4580	199	12	5010	4600	17	12
					500	50	21	1	50	40	2	1

Returning to the "false" Ser. A-solutions, it is interesting to see the mean S- and nl-values in Table 4. The S-values are significantly enhanced, and it should be possible to reject a larger portion of the false solutions. (At low ecliptic latitude, the sensitivity pattern for double stars is rather grid-like, however, and a number of the false solutions may have normal S-values. Cf. Lindegren's 1982 Strasbourg paper). In a majority of cases, the false solution has too large separation, and it may help also to reject any solution with $\text{sep} > 1.5$ arcsec.

Table 4. Mean S- and nl-values for correct and false Ser A-solutions. (Mean errors in parentheses).

Sep(")	S _{true}	S _{false}	nl _{true}	nl _{false}
0.9-1.1	4650(60)	4970(60)	14(1)	16(3)
1.1-1.3	4760(40)	5030(50)	14(2)	18(2)

6. The astrometric accuracy

Through the many program changes, I have tried to collect the astrometric results as given by the mean rms deviation (computed-true) in the five astrometric parameters. To simplify further, the accumulated results are again rms-means over a number of solutions in a specific range of separations. Most runs have been made for the equal-magnitude (Ser. C) case, and Table 5 gives such accumulated rms-values. (The results for each run are either a photocentric and a relative error, or two equivalent component-errors).

Table 5. Mean (rms) astrometric deviations (mas) for Ser. C runs with 11 unknowns. The numbers in parentheses are the total number of results in each mean, and the three columns are for individual, photocentric and relative data.

Sep(")	pr/sec	pc	rel
0.1-0.2	2.82 (96)	0.49 (74)	4.47 (46)
0.2-0.3	1.41 (102)	0.57 (58)	2.14 (51)
0.3-0.4	1.19 (58)	0.61 (30)	1.54 (26)
0.4-0.6	0.92 (100)	0.63 (55)	1.28 (50)
0.6-0.9	0.81 (134)	0.69 (65)	1.01 (67)
0.9-1.1	0.91 (104)	0.95 (52)	1.20 (52)
1.1-1.3	1.60 (52)	1.07 (26)	2.99 (26)

For comparison, Table 6 gives some collected results for the "old" runs in Section 1. The separation-intervals are not quite identical, but the qualitative agreement is good: The results in Table 5 (with 1 parallax and 4 p.m components) are intermediate between the "free" (2 par., 4 p.m), and "fixed" (1 par., 2 p.m) solutions of Table 6.

Table 6. Mean (rms) astrometric deviations (mas) for Ser. C runs with 12 ("free") or 9 ("fixed") unknowns. Both columns refer to individual component data.

Sep(")	free	fix
0.2-0.3	1.97 (14)	1.39 (14)
0.3-0.6	1.02 (52)	0.82 (36)
0.6-0.9	0.99 (52)	0.75 (42)
0.9-1.2	1.06 (44)	0.83 (26)
1.2-2.0	1.22 (40)	0.95 (30)

Tables 7 and 8 give similar means for Ser. A and B, only somewhat less accurate due to the fewer number of runs.

Table 7. Mean (rms) astrometric deviations (mas) for Ser. B ($\Delta m=1.5$). The two first columns are for primary and secondary, and the last two give photocentric and relative errors. (The numbers in parentheses are the number of results included in each mean).

Sep(")	pr	sec	pc	rel
0.1-0.2	4.94 (33)	15.9 (33)	0.66 (31)	21.5 (31)
0.2-0.3	1.56 (22)	6.77 (22)	0.88 (20)	6.53 (20)
0.3-0.4	1.00 (19)	3.46 (19)	0.95 (17)	3.58 (17)
0.4-0.6	0.82 (24)	3.28 (24)	1.41 (20)	3.10 (20)
0.6-0.9	0.79 (28)	2.95 (28)	1.53 (26)	2.70 (26)
0.9-1.1	0.79 (19)	3.23 (19)	1.96 (19)	3.20 (19)
1.1-1.3	0.84 (20)	3.31 (20)	2.22 (20)	3.56 (20)

Table 8. As Table 7, but for Ser. A-runs ($\Delta m=3.0$).

Sep(")	pr	sec	pc	rel
0.1-0.2	4.81 (17)	53.5 (17)	0.73 (17)	56.8 (17)
0.2-0.3	1.22 (13)	17.9 (13)	0.87 (13)	18.2 (13)
0.3-0.4	0.80 (13)	14.0 (13)	1.02 (13)	13.9 (13)
0.4-0.6	0.77 (17)	11.2 (17)	1.16 (17)	11.2 (17)
0.6-0.9	0.80 (16)	10.5 (16)	1.40 (16)	10.5 (16)
0.9-1.1	0.85 (8)	12.1 (8)	1.88 (8)	12.0 (8)
1.1-1.3	0.61 (10)	11.7 (10)	2.39 (10)	11.9 (10)

The data in Tables 5-8 show a similar trend with separation. The smallest rms-values (for separate components) occur at sep=0".4-0".9, and there is a large error-increase as the separations get smaller. This is mostly due to increasing correlations among the parameters for the two stars, and for these close systems, the astrometric data for the photocentre are much more accurate. At larger separations (1"-1".3), the component errors increase again, especially for small Δm .

An important question is also how the above "real" astrometric errors compare with the formal ones computed in the LS-solution. As a measure of this, another χ^2 -measure is defined by the sum

$$\chi_{\text{astr}}^2 = \sum \left(\frac{\text{true error}}{\text{calc m.e.}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

over the five astrometric parameters. Ideally, we would have $\chi_{\text{astr}}^2 = 5$, and we define the "error increase factor"

$$f_e = \left(\frac{\chi_{\text{astr}}^2}{5} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Roughly, then, the formal mean errors in the astrometric parameters have to be multiplied by f_e to give the real errors. Table 9 gives f_e for three ranges of separation and three different Δm -values as computed from straight means of χ_{astr}^2 . For the individual components, the f_e -values are satisfyingly close to unity, with sensible increases only for a faint component at small separation. For the photocentre, however, f_e increases rapidly with the separation. This seems to be due to small systematic errors in the solution for the magnitude-difference between the components. The position of the photocentre is very sensitive to this intensity-ratio and a systematic shift of size 0.02 Δm (as observed for sep=0".5-1".1) is sufficient to cause the large f_e -values in Table 9. The Δm -errors are much larger (and negative) at the smallest separations, but the effect on the photocentre is less apparent.

Table 9. Error multiplication factors f_e for primary, secondary and photocentric solutions, as function of separation and magnitude difference.

		0.1-0.3	0.3-0.9	0.9-1.3
pr	$\Delta m=0.$	1.2	1.1	1.2
	$\Delta m=1.5$	1.2	1.2	1.2
	$\Delta m=3.$	1.4	1.2	1.2
sec	$\Delta m=0.$	1.2	1.1	1.2
	$\Delta m=1.5$	1.3	1.2	1.1
	$\Delta m=3.$	1.9	1.1	1.1
pc	$\Delta m=0.$	0.8	1.0	1.8
	$\Delta m=1.5$	0.9	1.9	3.6
	$\Delta m=3.$	0.9	1.5	3.3

7. Computing times

With the present programs, each LS-iteration takes about 38 seconds CPU-time on the HP 9000 of Lund Observatory. Using the mean number of iterations given in Table 2, we get the following timing estimates (mean over all Δm).

Table 10. Estimated mean CPU-time to find a binary solution at different separations.

Sep(")	CPU-time(min)
0.1-0.2	11
0.2-0.3	7
0.3-0.4	7
0.4-0.6	12
0.6-0.9	23
0.9-1.1	38
1.1-1.3	51

From existing statistics, one may predict (cf. NDAC/LO/039) that the closer binaries will predominate. With such a distribution, the mean CPU-time may be about 15 minutes per binary. This may still be too large, and it is probably better not to use the individual frame-data (as at present), but rather to average the Fourier coefficients over each FOV-passage. This will reduce the number of observations by a factor of eight, and all computations will be correspondingly faster. This will be tested in practice in a later study.

8. Conclusions

The main conclusions from the present study are:

1. For known binaries, the a priori positions need to be known to within about $0''.3$ in order for the LS-solution to converge.
2. For unknown "simple" binaries (no extra components, linear approximation for the orbital motion), a "grid-search" for reasonable start values will mostly lead to a correct and convergent LS-solution if the separation is below some 1.2 arcsec and the magnitude-difference less than some 2.5 magnitudes.
3. Systems with faint secondaries require some extra care to exclude "false" solutions.
4. The somewhat large computing-times may probably be reduced with a more optimized program-structure.

The next steps in complexity are

- a) orbital motion with appreciable curvature
- b) more than two components

These effects will be studied in subsequent papers.